

**PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF 'GHARKUL YOJANA' FOR TRIBAL PEOPLE: A
CASE STUDY OF DAHANU TALUKA**

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Abstract

Pradhan Mantra Awas Yojana (PMAY) aims at providing a pucca house, with basic amenities, to all poor houseless households. The scheme of IAY (Indira Awas Yojana) has been re-structured into Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana (PMAY) from 1st April 2016. It is also called as Gharkul Yojana. In this study an attempt is made to study the performance evaluation of 'Gharkul Yojana' for Tribal People. Therefore field survey was conducted at Dahanu taluka of Palghar District. The field survey result concludes that the Gharkul scheme of government has solved housing problem of tribal family. But the amount received under this scheme for construction of house is not sufficient.

Key words: Pradhan Mantra Awas Yojana (PMAY), Indira Awas Yojana (IAY), Gharkul Yojana

1.0 Introduction:

The Tribal or 'Adivashi' are one of the most marginalised communities in India. The constitution of India used the term '[Scheduled Tribes](#)' (STs) for 'Adivashi' tribes of India. The schedule V and VI of Indian Constitution provides special protection. The tribal communities in India live in about 15% of land in various geo-climatic conditions ranging from plains to hill areas. There is wide diversity of culture, traditions, and livelihood system of tribal societies in India. A majority of the Scheduled Tribe (ST) population in India is concentrated in the eastern, central and western belt covering the nine States such as: Odisha, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh and West Bengal. According to 2011 census, the schedule tribes accounted for 104.3 million populations i.e. 8.6% of total population of country.

Considering a poor proliferation of tribal societies, the state and central Government of India chalked out a comprehensive plans and schemes for the development of tribal people in India. Yet it is seen that tribal are most backward community in India. On this backdrop an attempt is made to study the evaluation of performance of Gharkul Yojana schemes in Maharashtra. Therefore a case study of Dahanu Taluks of Palghar district is selected for presented study.

2.0 Significance of Study:

Indian society is pluralistic society. India as see today consists of several groups with different regional and cultural identities. Tribal community is one of important characteristics of Indian culture. India is

having second largest concentration of tribal population in the world. But generally it is seen that, As compared to other sections of the Indian Society, Tribal population has the lowest Human Development Index (HDI). Various efforts have been made in every five year plans for the developments of tribal. Despite of all such efforts a large segment of the tribal population still lives below poverty line. It suggests the need for conducting a scientific enquiry or study to evaluate the existing tribal schemes. The present research is useful to identify the prevailing socio economic conditions of tribal and to study the awareness programmes on the development schemes to the Tribal. Also to identify the loop whole of the development schemes.

3.0 Tribal Development Schemes:

Programmes or Schemes of Central Government:

The Ministry of Tribal Affairs, Government of India is providing assistance to the State Government every year under following schemes-

3.1 Special Central Assistance (SCA) to Tribal sub plan (TSP):-

The Ministry of Tribal Affairs, GOI provides SCA to the state Government as an additive to the state TSP. This scheme has been launched by the GOI since 1977-78. It is a 100 % Central Assisted scheme. This is primarily family oriented income generation scheme in sector of agriculture, horticulture, sericulture animal husbandry and co-operation. Below poverty line tribal population should alone be supported with SCA financed activities. Also for, creation of critical infrastructure in tribal area and to extend financial assistance to Self Help Groups (SHGs), community based activities, Primitive Tribal Groups and Forest Villages.

This SCA grant is utilized for economic development of:

- Integrated Tribal Development Agency (ITDA),
- Tribal Development Project (ITDP),
- Modified Area Development Approach (MADA) Pockets and Clusters, PVTGs and dispersed tribal population.

3.2 Central Assistance under Article 275(1) of the Constitution of India:-

According to Article 275 of the Indian Constitution Grant in aid is given by the union to certain states. It is charged to Consolidated Fund of India (except northern Eastern state) and is an additive to State Plan funds and efforts for Tribal Development. The need of assistance and different sums may be fixed for different states. In short, this grant is additionality to normal central assistance to the state plan. It is given to 100 % Central Assisted scheme for strengthening the infrastructure in the sectors critical to enhancement of human development indices.

The funds are released for a) Specific welfare projects of the STs b) Strengthening of administration of tribal area, and c) Establishing Eklavya Model Residential Schools. The funds under this scheme are utilized for ITDA, ITDP, and MADA and for PVTGs.

3.3 Central Assistance for Conservation-cum Development of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs)-

This scheme was started in 1998-99. It is a 100% Central sector Scheme for exclusive development of PVTGs. The scheme was revised in 2015, to make it more effective. The scheme covers only the 75 identified Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups. The scheme is focus on developmental activity for PVTGs, viz., housing, land distribution, land development, agricultural growth, cattle development, increasing connectivity, and installation of non-conventional sources of energy for lighting purpose, social security or any other innovative activity meant for the comprehensive socio-economic development of PVTGs.

4.0 Demographic Profile of Dahanu Taluka:

Table no, 1.0

Population of Dahanu Taluka

Population Type	Male Population	Female Population	Total Population
Rural	1,66,991	1,71,171	3,38,162
Urban	32,583	31,350	63,933
Total	1,99,574	2,02,521	4,02,095

Source: <https://villageinfo.in/maharashtra/thane/dahanu.html>

The above table no. 1.0 shows population of Dahanu Taluka. As per census 2011, the total population of Dahanu taluka was 402095 of which 49.63 % accounted by male and 50.36% by female which is marginally more than male population. It is also seen that 84.10 % of Dahanu taluka living in rural area while 15.89% population living in urban area.

Table no.1.2

Category wise Population in Dahanu Taluka

	Population	Percentage
SC Population	6,513	1.62%
ST Population	277,904	69.11%
Non-SC/ST Population	117678	29.27%
Total Population	4,02,095	100%

Reference : Census of india, 2011

The above table no.1.2 Shows category wise Population in Dahanu taluka. It is seen that most of population belong to ST cast that is 69.11 %, followed by non-SC/ ST population i.e. 29.27%. The population of SC category is very less 1.62%.

5.0 Objectives of Study:

- (1) To study the social and economic development of Tribal society in Dahanu Taluka
- (3) To assess the performance of Gharkul Scheme for tribal people in Dahanu taluka.
- (4) To suggest measures for effective implementation of the Scheme.

6.0 Hypothesis:

- **Ho:** Amount received under this scheme for construction of house is not sufficient.
- **Ho:** Tribal people are not satisfied about the financial assistance received under Gharkul Scheme of Government.

7.0 Research Methodology:

The various building blocks of the proposed study are:

- (1) **Universe:** The universe for the present study is confined to Dahanu taluka of Palghar Districts of Maharashtra. As per the Census India 2011, Dahanu Taluka has 82,139 households, population of 4,02,095 of which 1,99,574 are males and 2,02,521 are females. There are 173 villages in Dahanu district.
- (2) **Sample:** As per record of ITDP Dahanu there are 44 beneficiaries of Gharkul Scheme in the year 2017-18. A sample of 44 respondents are selected from 173 villages of Dahanu taluka.
- (3) **Nature of Research:** The proposed research is exploratory as it tries to probe into the recent schemes of the Government of India towards tribal development. The proposed study has analysed the Gharkul Scheme quantitatively and qualitatively to measure its success.
- (4) **Data Need:** The present research/study has made use of both primary as well as secondary data.
 - **Primary data** is collected through field survey conducted with the help of well-designed pre tested and closed-ended questionnaire. The likert scale is used in design the questionnaire.
 - **Secondary data** is collected from various published sources of the Maharashtra government and official agencies. The secondary data and information is collected from following sources: Annual reports of government of India, Ministry of tribal affairs. Census of India, 2011
- (5) **Statistical Tools:** To process and analyse the data the researcher contemplates to use various statistical tools as per necessity such as: Percentage and Chi- Squared techniques.

8.0 Review of Literature:

Sangeeta Vaishnav and Meenu Srivastava (2014)¹: The present study was conducted in Maharashtra as the higher concentration of the warli artisans found in Dhanu, Jawahar, Manor and kosbad Villages of Thane district to assess the socioeconomic profile of warli artisans. Tribal art generally reflects the creative energy found in rural areas that acts as an undercurrent to the craftsmanship of the tribal people. Warli painting is the famous folk art of Maharashtra. Warli is the name of the largest tribe found on the northern outskirts of Mumbai, in Western India. The growing popularity and commercialization of the Warli paintings will uphold bright potentials for their upliftment of these tribal people and will help in integrating them with the mainstream.

Sharmishtha L. Matkar (2017)²: The study concludes that the programmes implemented have been criticised for being partial as they do not accommodate the tribal lifestyle and means. It is feared that the uneducated tribal population at large will find it difficult to cope with the industrial or corporate set-up. There is some resistance from the tribal's themselves to the help offered, as well. For instance, the government provides good quality of food supplements; they are sweetened to tempt the children to consume them regularly. However, the preferred taste for the tribal is savoury, and so they do not consume the supplements as regularly as they should.

Adam A. Semlambo (2018)³: In his extensive research on the Warli tribe in Dahanu taluka. Study concludes that the natural resources and wildlife of the region influences their culture in terms of artwork, artefacts like musical instruments and the folktales that have come to them from their forefathers. The spectrum of wildlife that they depict in their drawings, are invariably those which are dangerous to human life and livelihood such as tiger, deer, snakes and scorpions. The strong depiction of village life is their strong association with agriculture on which the Warlis have survived for so many generations. For them their paddy lands are a source of their very livelihood and they continue to thus, depict this even today the reason for the loss of the culture in sections of the Warli belt is attributed to the diminishing appreciation of their traditional values by the younger generations of the Warli people.

9.0 Demographic Profile of Respondents:

Table no. 1.3

Educational qualification of the respondents

Education level	Number of (In Percent)
SSC	27.27
HSSC	31.82
UG	22.73
PG	18.18
Total	100 (44)

Source: Primary data collected through field survey

It is clear from the above table no.5.71 and figure no.5.27 that out of the 44 respondents surveyed, 31.82 % of the respondents are HSSC qualified. 27.27 % are SSC qualified. 22.73% of the respondents are under graduate while 18.8 % of respondents are post graduate.

9.1 Gender-wise classification:

The gender-wise distribution of selected respondents is presented as below.

Table no. 1.4

Gender-wise classification

Gender	Number of respondents (%)
Male	72.73
Female	27.27
Total	100(44)

Source: Primary data collected through field survey

Table no. 5.73 shows the gender-wise distribution of the respondents. Out of 44 respondents, majority of respondents that is 72.73 respondents are belong to male category. And remaining 27.27 % respondents belong to female category

9.2 Ration card wise distribution of respondents:

Table no 1.5

Ration card wise distribution of respondents

Ration card	Number of respondents	%
a)Yellow	44	100
b)Orange	0	
c) White	0	

Source:Primary data collected through field survey

Table no. 5.73 shows the gender-wise distribution of the respondents . Out of 44 respondents, majority of respondents that is 44 (i.e. 100%) respondents are belong to Yellow ration card holder. And

9.3 Size of Family of Respondents:

Table no. 1.6

Size of Family of Respondents:

Size of family	Number of respondents
2 to 04 Members	40.91
04 to 06 Members	59.09
06 to 8 Members	0
Total	100 (44)

Source:Primary data collected through field survey

Table no. 1.7 shows the gender-wise distribution of the respondents Out of 44 respondents, majority of respondents that is 59.9 % respondents are belong to family size of 04 to 06 members. And remaining 40.91% respondents belong to 02 to 04 members.

10.0 Awareness about Scheme Housing Scheme

Table no. 1.7

Housing grant (Gharkul Yojana) received by you from which of the following scheme .

Scheme	a) Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY)	b) Shabari Awas Yojana (SAY)	c) Name of scheme don't know	Total respondents
Number of respondents	68.18 %	6.82	25.00	100(44)

Source:Primary data collected through field survey

It is clear from above table no.1.8 that out of total 44 respondents 68.18% respondents are saying that they received grants from PMAY scheme. 6.82 % respondents are saying that they received grants from SAY

scheme. While rest of 25 % respondents received grants but don't know (unaware about) name of scheme.

11.0 Performance of 'Gharkul' Yojana for Tribal People:

The result of primary survey about performance of Gharkul scheme for tribal people is summarised below.

Table no. 1.8

Performance of 'Gharkul' Yojana for tribal people:

	Name of scheme	Number of Respondents (%)					Total Respondents
		A	DA	N	SA	SD	
	Gharkul Scheme						
1	The grant received by you under this scheme for construction of your house is sufficient.	18	45	23	5	9	44
2	Bathroom and toilets facility also constructed from this gharkul grant.	73	9	5	14	0	44
3	Are the Widows are prioritized in Gharkul scheme.	50	9	30	6	5	44
4	One can construct house of his/ her choice From the received grant.	41	36	23	0	0	44
5	There is bias in selection of beneficiaries of gharkul scheme.	41	15	18	8	18	44
6	Garkul scheme is effectively implemented by Grampanchayat .	18	50	23	5	5	44
7	Construction of house under Garkul scheme by contractor is convenient.	9	55	18	0	18	44
8	Gharkul scheme of government has solved housing problem of my family.	73	9	0	18	0	44
9	Due to Gharkul scheme there is rise in my house tax payment to gram Panchyat.	27	5	18	41	9	44

Source: Values are calculated through primary data

Note: **A:** agree, **DA:** Disagree Agree, **N:** Neutral, **SA:** Strongly Agree, **SD:** Strongly Disagree

The researcher asked the respondents to rate the Performance of 'Gharkul' Yojana for Tribal People Dahanu Taluka on the 5-point Likert's Scale. Out of 44 respondents,

45 % and 05 % respondents respectively rated disagree and strongly disagree, that the grant received under the scheme for construction of house is sufficient. Their percentage to total respondents is 50%. Therefore, it is concluded that amount received under this scheme for construction of house is not sufficient.

73 % and 14 % respondents respectively rated agree and strongly disagree, that Bathroom and toilets facility also constructed from this Gharkul grant.

50% and 06 % respondents respectively rated agree and strongly agree that the widows are prioritized in Gharkul scheme. Their percentage to total respondents is 56%.

41% respondents are agree, that they can construct house of his/ her choice from the received grant. While, 36 % respondents are disagree. Remaining 23% respondent are neither agree or disagree

41% and 08 % respondents respectively rated agree and strongly agree that there is bias in selection of beneficiaries of Gharkul scheme. Their percentage to total respondents is 49%. While, 15 % and 18% respondents are disagree and strongly disagree. Remaining 18% respondent are neither agree or disagree. 50 % and 5% respondents rated disagree and strongly disagree respectively, that Garkul scheme is effectively implemented by Grampanchayat. Their percentage to total respondents is 55 %. While, 18 % and 5% respondents are agree and strongly agree. Remaining 23% respondent are neither agree or disagree 55 % and 18% respondents rated disagree and strongly disagree respectively, that Construction of house under Garkul scheme by contractor is convenient. While, 9 % respondents are agree. Remaining 18 % respondent are neither agree or disagree

73% and 18 % respondents respectively rated agree and strongly agree, that Gharkul scheme of government has solved housing problem of their family. While, 9 % respondents are disagree.

27% and 41 % respondents rated agree and strongly agree respectively, that Due to Gharkul scheme there is rise in house tax payment to Gram Panchyat. While, 5% and 9 % respondents respectively are disagree and strongly disagree. Remaining 18% respondent are neither agree or disagree.

12.0 Size of the family and Level of Satisfaction

Size of the family and Level of Satisfaction with grant received under Garkul scheme from government With a view to find the degree of association between the gender of the respondents and their level of satisfaction, a two-way table was prepared and the result is depicted in the following table.

Table 1.9

Size of the family and level of satisfaction about grant under Gharkul scheme.

(two-way table)

Gender	Level of Satisfaction			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
2 to 04 Members	02	10	06	18
04 to 06 Members	02	16	08	26
Total	04	26	14	44

Source: Calculated from primary data

Size of the family gender and level of satisfaction about grant received under Gharkul Scheme (chi-square test)

Factor	Calculated χ^2 Value	P Value	Result
Size of the family	0.2232	0.894419	Not Significant at 5% level of Significance

Source: Values are calculated through primary data

It is found from the above table that the p value is 0.89449 which is greater than the 0.05. Thus we conclude that Size of the family and the level of satisfaction about government grants under Gharkul scheme are not

associated”.

Conclusion:

It is conclude that amount received under this scheme for construction of house is not sufficient. The widows are prioritized in Gharkul scheme. The Bathroom and toilets facility also available to tribals from this ‘Gharkul scheme’. The Garkul scheme is effectively implemented by Grampanchayat but there is bias in selection of beneficiaries of Gharkul scheme. The Gharkul scheme of government has solved housing problem of tribal family. The size of the family and the level of satisfaction about government grants under ‘Gharkul scheme’ are not associated

Reference:

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